

Determination of the efficient exploitation period of buses taking into account the complexity of the route

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Abstract

The operating conditions of the city bus routes are of different levels of complexity, planning of the traffic structure, taking measures for fast and safe movement along the route are envisaged. In addition, the standardization of the quality level of services requires a specific approach and the introduction of fair systems of financial support from the state. Currently, the methods and technologies recommended by researchers to evaluate the processes of efficient use of motor vehicles are aimed at conducting complex tests. In addition to requiring specialists with special knowledge, there is a need for universal methods of evaluating the processes of efficient use of motor vehicles for the effective cooperation of the competent authorities regulating the activities of urban public transport and service transport operators.

Keywords: Urban public transport, route complexity, technical life of a motor vehicle, economic life of a motor vehicle, effective service time, route complexity index, operating costs.

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INTRODUCTION

In the world's major megalopolises, all the constituent elements of the industry have been continuously researched by world industry experts for many years, for the efficient organization of the urban public transport system, the safe and reliable operation of buses that are widely used as public transport for many years [1-10]. In our previous studies, the concepts of "economic" and "technical" life were included in determining the period of use of light vehicles in various operational processes, and an evaluation methodology was developed based on the distance covered or the period of operation. Accordingly, the term "technical life" of automobiles means the period during which automobiles can be technically used, i.e., the period until the automobile is physically completely destroyed [7]. And their "economic life" is the period of use from which economic benefits can be obtained from cars, and it can also be called "effective service life of cars". Logically, the "economic life" of cars is shorter than the "technical life". Also, the emergence of new and high-performance models, various social or environmental quality requirements imposed by society require replacement of these vehicles even before the end of their "economic life".

It is known that the increase in the period of use of motor vehicles and the complexity of the operational conditions in the directions they move lead to an increase in maintenance and repair costs, as well as wear and tear of mechanisms and aggregates, to an increase in the consumption of fuel and lubricants. The most important thing is that these indicators are manifested in different degrees under the influence of the background of various complexities in the exploitation process. In this case, the calculation of the amount of expenses requires the calculation of the distance traveled by the vehicles, taking into account the complications that exist in the distance traveled. In practice, the costs of maintenance and repair of cars are calculated according to the distance traveled and include:

- labor costs for maintenance and repair work;
- consumption of spare parts and materials;
- cost of service of service enterprises.

Car maintenance and repair costs per kilometer driven are "variable", and costs increase as the car "ages".

If a motor transport enterprise buys new vehicles at the expense of its own funds, bank loans, leasing or investments from other external investors, the economic life of the motor transport means additional operating costs, depreciation costs, interest on loan or lease payments for every 1 km traveled. the size is determined by the period until the smallest amount.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Research conducted on the evaluation of the effective operation of public transport shows that it is important to take into account the existing conditions during their operation when determining the service life of buses. However, the operational conditions of transport visas require evaluation based on different indicators based on the transport formula (driver+vehicle+passenger+road+environment+pedestrian). In our previous research, we presented a simple estimation method that takes into account all factors of route complexity [11]. According to it, the complexity of the route can be estimated by the ratio of the total time lost to pass the obstacles to cover the distance from point A to point B along the route with the specified technical speed, regardless of the type of factors in the operational conditions.

The time spent on stops per route can be calculated as follows:

$$t_m = \sum_{i=1}^n m_i p_i t_i \quad (1)$$

where: t_m - total time spent on stops, hours;

m_i - number of stops of type i ;

p_i - Probability level of stops of type i ;

t_i - Average time spent on stops of type i , hours.

In this case, the route complexity index can be calculated as follows:

$$I_m = \frac{t_m}{t_u} \quad (2)$$

where: t_u - total time spent for one trip in the direction, hours.
 The logical confirmation of the above considerations and the mathematical model for calculating the effective operational age of the buses offered based on them, taking into account the route complexity index present in the operational processes, can be expressed as follows:

$$\frac{B_{ab} + \sum_{i=1}^N (S + \Delta S_i)}{\sum_{i=1}^N L_{o.r.t.yil_i} * I_m} \rightarrow \min \quad (3) \quad N=1..k$$

The following conditions must be met for the economic significance of this model to be substantial:

- the "economic life" of the bus is less than or equal to its "technical life" - $N \leq k$;
- for the calculations to be simple and convenient, regardless of the age of the car, its residual value is taken as $V_{qol}=0$.

where:

N – effective operating period of the bus, year;

K – period of usable "technical life" of the bus, years;

S – the annual stated costs under specific operating conditions are taken for the base period, thousand soums/km;

ΔS_i – The amount of additional operating expenses for the i -th year, taking into account the effect of route complexity, thousand soums/km;

$L_{av,year}$ – average annual distance of the bus, thousand km;

I_m - routing complexity index;

B_{ab} – purchase price of the bus, thousand soums;

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the above expression, we will calculate the effective operating period of the "Mercedes Benz O 345C" bus, which has been used for passenger transportation in Tashkent for many years (Table 1).

№	Routes	14	17	24	60	63	72	89	96
1	Route complexity, %	0,46	0,58	0,63	0,48	0,47	0,64	0,49	0,44
2	Route length (km)	14,4	21,2	24,8	14,2	19,8	17,1	17,4	21,8
3	Annual average distance of the bus (km)	75000	75000	75000	75000	75000	75000	75000	75000
4	Initial price of the bus (in thousands of soums)	1438.5	1438.5	1438.5	1438.5	1438.5	1438.5	1438.5	1438.5
5	Total expenses other than amortization in 1 trip (in thousand of soums)	205	299	328	202	248	237	247	259
6	Amount of expenses corresponding to 1 km (soums)	14231	14093	13220	14225	12538	13860	14172	11877
7	Average annual cost growth (7%)	996	987	925	996	878	970	992	831
8	Annual total expenses (in thousands of soums)	74710	73990	69404	74683	65824	72763	74405	62355

Table 1. Effective operating period of the "Mercedes Benz O345C" bus.

Based on the information obtained on the assessment of the change of the effective operating period of buses under the influence of the complexity of the route, it is possible to observe the difference in the costs of buses operating on certain routes (in the example of Mercedes-Benz O345) (Table 2).

Based on the results of the analysis, it can be noted that in determining the effective technical and economic life of buses, it is not a correct approach to take into account only their total distance traveled. One of the most important tasks is to determine the real value of the work done in the introduction of effective mechanisms of today's complex state and private sector management form based on the principles of market economy.

CONCLUSIONS

Therefore, taking into account all the specific features of the service processes with the help of the wide introduction of modern information technologies into the processes of the city public transport service, drawing conclusions based on the obtained data by conducting various comparative analyzes serves as a guarantee of achieving fair and positive results.

Table 2. Section of routes belonging to the bus palace #2 in the city of Tashkent.

№ 14				
№	Average annual distance traveled, km	Total annual operating expenses, thousand soums	Total annual expenses, thousand soums	Total costs corresponding to 1 km distance, thousand soums
1	75000	1068825	2507325	33,43
2	150000	2210860	3649360	24,33
3	225000	3427605	4866105	21,63
4	300000	4719060	6157560	20,53
5	375000	6085225	7523725	20,06
6	450000	7526100	8964600	19,92
7	525000	9041685	10480185	19,96
8	600000	10631980	12070480	20,12
9	675000	12296985	13735485	20,35

№ 72				
№	Average annual distance traveled, km	Total annual operating expenses, thousand soums	Total annual expenses, thousand soums	Total costs corresponding to 1 km distance, thousand soums
1	75000	1039500	2478000	33,04
2	150000	2151767	3590267	23,94
3	225000	3336793	4775293	21,22
4	300000	4594582	6033082	20,11
5	375000	5925134	7363634	19,64
6	450000	7328449	8766949	19,48
7	525000	8804527	10243027	19,51
8	600000	10353368	11791868	19,65
9	675000	11974972	13413472	19,87

№ 63				
№	Average annual distance traveled, km	Total annual operating expenses, thousand soums	Total annual expenses, thousand soums	Total costs corresponding to 1 km distance, thousand soums
1	75000	940350	2378850	31,72
2	150000	1946524	3385024	22,57
3	225000	3018522	4457022	19,81
4	300000	4156344	5594844	18,65
5	375000	5359990	6798490	18,13
6	450000	6629460	8067960	17,93
7	525000	7964754	9403254	17,91
8	600000	9365872	10804372	18,01

№ 96				
№	Average annual distance traveled, km	Total annual operating expenses, thousand soums	Total annual expenses, thousand soums	Total costs corresponding to 1 km distance, thousand soums
1	75000	890775	2329275	31,06
2	150000	1843905	3282405	21,88
3	225000	2859390	4297890	19,10
4	300000	3937230	5375730	17,92
5	375000	5077425	6515925	17,38
6	450000	6279975	7718475	17,15
7	525000	7544880	8983380	17,11
8	600000	8872140	10310640	17,18
9	675000	10261755	11700255	17,33

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